

The current sociotechnical ecosystem presents trends that, if confirmed by the speculated date, will generate implications. Develop a list of these implications, considering the possible impacts resulting from the consolidation of these trends in the future.

ID	Implication	Classification	Magnitude

Notebook 2

Group:

Speculated Date:

The **classification** categorizes each implication as *positive*, *negative*, or *desirable*.

The **magnitude** categorizes the degree of impact, which may be *low*, *medium*, or *high*.

Activity Flow

